

FROM THE HISTORY OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract: The article provides information on the emergence and development of the oil industry in the Fergana Valley, which has unique natural and geographical features. The author, having analyzed historical sources, highlights the local characteristics of oil production in this region.

Keywords: Fergana Valley, oil, gas, well, "Chimion," "Rishtan," "Bitum," "Uzbekneftegaz."

In accordance with the Action Strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of changes have been implemented in the oil and gas industry. In particular, the management system of the joint-stock company "Uzbekneftegaz" was improved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Improve the Management System of the Oil and Gas Sector" dated June 30, 2017 [1].

It is well known that the Fergana Valley has long been a region rich in natural resources. This article discusses the history of oil and gas production in the Fergana Valley.

First of all, it should be noted that information about the use of oil by the peoples of Central Asia is found in ancient and early medieval sources. For example, the ancient Greek historian and philosopher Plutarch, while describing Alexander the Great's campaign through Central Asia to India (323-327 BC), notes

that in several locations along the Oxus (Amu Darya) River, a liquid resembling real oil was found seeping from the ground.

Until the mid-19th century, the extraction of oil products in the Kokand Khanate was considered arduous work, and local craftsmen extracted oil using very primitive methods. Specifically, they would fill oil-bearing wells with water and collect the floating oil using brooms. At the "Moybuloq" field, located 40 km from Namangan, up to 60 poods (960 kg) of oil per day were extracted using this method[2]. Additionally, oil was extracted near the village of Romitan in the Kokand district. On average, about 2 buckets of oil accumulated in local wells daily. The extracted oil was transported by cart to Margilan, where it was heated in special vessels to obtain kerosene.

In the village of Kamishboshi in the Fergana Valley, in the early 1880s, Russian entrepreneur D.P. Petrov extracted up to 10 poods (160 kg) of oil per day from two wells up to 25 meters deep. From 1880 to 1883, the number of these wells increased to four. The boreholes were drilled using percussion methods. Their walls were lined with wooden planks, and oil was extracted using special long buckets (bads). According to some sources, up to 5-10 tons of oil were extracted from such wells daily.[3]

In 1885, the Russian businessman D.P. Petrov drilled two wells in Shorsu, extracting 400-500 kg of oil per day. Kerosene and fuel oil were produced from this oil in a special boiler. Therefore, historical sources indicate that the beginning of the oil industry in Uzbekistan dates back to 1885[4].

The first oil field in Uzbekistan was discovered in 1904 at the Chimyon field (formerly known as Vannovsky) in the Fergana Valley at a depth of 278 meters. This field produced about 130 tons of oil daily. In the same year, an oil refinery was commissioned near the Oltiariq railway station. According to some experts, the formation of the oil industry in Uzbekistan began precisely on this date. Kerosene was the main product obtained from refined oil. Kerosene and residual fuel oil were

loaded onto carts and camels and sold in the markets of Central Asia, Afghanistan, and China, as well as to cotton ginning plants, oil mills, and the general population in Tashkent, Andijan, and Kokand. Oil residues were used as fuel in railway transport. Later, several fields were discovered in the Fergana Basin (in the Yorquton and Maylisoy areas near Chimyon), the Chimyon-Oltiariq oil pipeline was built, and the oil refinery was expanded. During this period, Russian and foreign investors took full control of oil extraction, processing, and the sale of petroleum products. In 1913, a total of 13 thousand tons of oil were extracted [5].

After the October Revolution in former Tsarist Russia, oil fields and oil refineries were transferred to state control, and the exploration and extraction of oil fields also came under Soviet authority. In subsequent years, new oil fields were discovered and quickly put into operation. The Altyaryk plant was expanded. During this period, the infrastructure of the oil industry was established in the republic. In 1941, 196 thousand tons of oil were extracted, and in 1945, this increased to 478 thousand tons. By 1950, oil production in Uzbekistan reached 1 million 342 thousand tons. From the 1950s, mechanization tools began to be used in oil fields, and turbine drilling methods were introduced [6].

In 1959, more than 1 million 460 thousand tons of oil were extracted from 9 oil fields in the Fergana Valley and Surkhandarya region alone. During this period, oil fields discovered in the Bukhara-Khiva territories were put into operation, and an oil and gas production department was established based on these. At the beginning of the 1970s, oil production decreased due to the depletion of reserves in some oil fields. To discover new oil deposits, it became necessary to drill deep wells. Ultra-deep oil wells were drilled to depths of 5200 meters in Vorukh, 5670 meters in Ghumkhana, 5805 meters in Chust-Pop, and 6006 meters in Mingbulak [7].

As can be seen from the presented data, the first oil and gas fields in Uzbekistan were discovered and put into operation in the Fergana Basin.

The use of natural gas in our republic first began in Fergana. In 1944, a gas pipeline was laid from the Andijan field in the Fergana Valley to the city of Andijan, and in 1951, gas extraction commenced at the Polvontosh field. In the Khovdok area of Surkhandarya, drilling of a deep exploration well began in 1933, and in 1934, oil gushed out from a depth of 158 meters. The four drilled wells started producing 75-100 tons of oil daily. Additionally, in 1936, the Uchqizil oil field was discovered north of Termez city, and in 1939, the Kukaydi oil field was found. Later, oil and gas fields such as Lalmikor, Amudarya, Kushtor, Mirshodi, and Gajak were discovered. Following the Fergana and Surkhandarya regions, geological exploration work was conducted on the Bukhara Tectonic Step in Western Uzbekistan.

The formation and development of the gas industry in Uzbekistan primarily began in 1953 with the discovery of the first gas field in the Setanlantepa area of the Kyzylkum Desert. Extensive work was carried out in the gas and oil regions of the Bukhara province. On October 17, 1956, a powerful gas fountain erupted from a 600-meter well in the Gazli field. This marked the beginning of a new era in Uzbekistan's gas industry [8].

Subsequently, in the Bukhara-Khiva region, the fields of Shurtan, Zevarda, Pamyk, Alan, Kokdumalak, Shimoliy Urtaulok, and Kruk were discovered and put into operation.

During the years of independence, several gas condensate fields such as Urga, Sharqiy Berdakh, Uchsoy, and Surgil were discovered in the Ustyurt region, and some of them were brought into production.

It is appropriate to directly link the development and progress of the oil and gas industry in Uzbekistan with the independence of our Republic and reflect on the significant achievements in this field in the subsequent years.

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, the development of the oil and gas industry became a crucial task. On December 23, 1992, the oil and

gas industry, along with all related enterprises and organizational institutions, were united under a single management system, and the Uzbekneftegaz Corporation was established. In 1993, oil gushed from the ultra-deep layers of the Fergana Depression (Mingbulak structure) (exploration and drilling operations continue).

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